

IMPLEMENTING BUILDING PERFORMANCE MODELLING THROUGH BIM METHODOLOGY AND ITS IMPLICATION ON BUILDING DESIGN PROCESS

Ekaterina Moskvina

Supervisor

Mitja Košir⁽¹⁾

(1) Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Abstract

Construction 4.0 requires new approaches and methods to achieve primary goals set for the industry, such as sustainable cities and communities, responsible consumption and production, climate actions, innovations. Although the performance-based design (PBD) approach is not new, it is innovative in how it faces these goals compared to the traditional approach. The study discusses the concept of performance-based design in general. It reviews the methods and tools that can support the PBD application in the early design stage, such as Integrated Design Process, Building Information Modelling and others.

This master thesis aims to clarify major differences between the conventional and the PBD approach when applied in the initial design stage. It identifies the benefits of the new approach and the limitations and difficulties when applied in practice. It identified issues of using PBD in practice throughout a survey of 43 respondents from 21 countries. Finally, it examines the ability and readiness of the PBD method to substitute the traditional design approach. It compares the two approaches with a practical hypothetical project of an office building in Mengeš, Slovenia.

The case study results are the workflow and a strategy proposed to apply the PBD approach in the early design stage. The strategy can be used regardless of the modelling and analysis tools and for the residential, commercial and public projects. It helps to explore vast design space relatively quickly to understand design trends and options with the greatest impact on future building performance.

Dissertation:

<https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/2021-EkaterinaMoskvina-Dissertation.pdf>

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/b8XOK-6ELOE>

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5705777